

Adherence to ARV among children and young people (15-24 years) in the South West Region (SWR) of Cameroon: comparing the self-report assessment scale (MMAS-4) and virtual analogue scale (VAS) in predicting viral suppression.

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ABSTRACT

Background

Optimal antiretroviral therapy (ART) adherence is mandatory to optimize patient outcomes. Poor ART adherence and worse treatment outcomes have been observed in children and adolescents. Diverse subjective methods are used to assess adherence in the absence of a gold standard method but there is limited information on effective methods in measuring ART adherence in this vulnerable population.

Objectives: This study assessed ART adherence using two self-reported methods and compared their ability to predict viral suppression.

Method

A facility-based cross-sectional and retrospective study was conducted in which 329 participants were consecutively recruited into the study between February to June 2023. A structured questionnaire was used to capture socio-demographic and treatment variables. Two self-report scales (MMAS-4 and VAS) and the viral load suppression were used in parallel to assess ART adherence in 329 participants after non-adherence was normalized to minimize social desirability effects. The Kappa statistics test and the Kendall's τ concordance tests were used to determine the agreement between the three measures.

Results: The adherence levels determined by the three methods; (self-report MMAS-4; VAS and Viral suppression) were, 70.5%, 69.0 %, and 71.5 % respectively. Based on Kappa statistics, the level of agreement between the adherence methods was poor; SR and VAS (Kappa=0.402, $p<0.001$), VL and SR (Kappa=0.201, $p<0.001$), VL and VAS (Kappa=0.352, $p<0.001$). SR and VAS had a better agreement seconded by VL and VAS. Respondents who had good ART adherence on VAS were 40 times as likely to achieve Viral Suppression.

Conclusion: ART adherence among children and young people in the South West Region was below the expected 95%. The level of agreement among adherence methods was poor with the highest agreement observed between the two subjective methods and least between the subjective and objective methods.

Keywords: HIV in children, young people, adolescents, adherence, self-reported adherence, viral load.

Introduction:

The burden of Human immunodeficiency virus (HIV) is still high in children and young people aged 10-24 years although great progress has been made in HIV response in Sub-Saharan countries. An estimated 270,000 children and adolescents were newly infected with HIV in 2022 (UNICEF, HIV STATISTIC-Global and Regional trends., 2023) (UNICEF, Global and Regional Trends : monitoring the situation of children and mothers., 2021). Globally, by the end of 2021, about 2.58 million children aged 0-19 years were living with HIV, 1.65 million of whom were adolescents aged 10 -19 years and in Cameroon, a total of 33,085 children aged 0-14 years and 18,043 adolescents 15-19 years were living with HIV (UNICEF, HIV STATISTIC-Global and Regional trends., 2023). Despite increased access to HIV medication, the decline in AIDS-related mortality among children and adolescents is slower compared to the adult population. Approximately 16% (99,840) of all AIDS related deaths (624,000) in 2022 were children under 20 years of age (Mirvat & Bartlett.A.W, 2020) (UNICEF, HIV STATISTIC-Global and Regional trends., 2023)

The current challenge of greater magnitude in HIV care and treatment is the very poor adherence (<95%) to the life-long ART observed in children, adolescents and young people compared to the adult population resulting in high viral load and worse HIV treatment outcomes (Mirvat & Bartlett.A.W, 2020) (WHO, 2022) (Daniel Schmidt1, et al., 2021) (Abreu, Vaz, Netto, & Brites, 2017) (OARAC, 2021). Optimal adherence of at least 95% to life-long ART is expected to achieve HIV treatment success, but many children and adolescents encounter varied difficulties in taking medication every day at a specific time (Achappa B, 2013). Globally, an estimated 62,3% of adolescents and young people are adherent to ART with the lowest rate of 53% in North America and the highest rate of 84% in Africa (Kim, Gerver, Fidler, & Ward, 2014). Self-reported adherence rates of 66.3 % and 82.9% were estimated among adolescents in the Centre and South West Regions of Cameroon respectively (Martial Wandji Lantche, 2021) (Mbuwir Charlotte Bongfen, 2021). ART Adherence among children and adolescents is not static and changes over time depending on life situations, developmental and environmental changes (Stirratt MJ C. J., 2018) (Gellad, Thorpe, Steiner, & Voils, 2017). It is therefore necessary to assess ART adherence of a client at every clinic visit to identify adherence barriers early and develop mitigation strategies. There is no singular gold standard method for assessing medication adherence but multiple

approaches have been developed and validated for use in different settings (Nassar, et al., 2022) (Saber P C. D., 2020). Adherence measurement is the proportion of pills swallowed over the pills expected to have been swallowed at the right time for a specific period (Anghel, 2019). There are varied methods of measuring adherence which are classified into subjective (indirect) and objective (directive) methods (Anghel, 2019). Direct methods of measuring adherence include directly observed therapy, detection of the drug or drug metabolite in a biological fluid, and detection of biological markers (viral load in plasma) (McRae-Clark AL, 2015) (Farmer, 1999) (Honghu Liu, et al., 2001). Indirect methods of assessing medication adherence include patient questionnaires, patient self-reports, pill counts, prescription refill rates, pharmacy refill records, electronic medication event monitoring systems and patient diaries (Maria L.S. Cruz a, 2014) (Anghel, 2019). (McRae-Clark AL, 2015) Indirect methods assess patients' pill-taking behaviour established usually with the help of a questionnaire. Indirect methods of ART adherence assessment rely on a patient's integrity and response and are therefore prone to recall bias, response bias and social desirability effects. (Al-Hassany L, 2019). Each method of adherence assessment has advantages and limitations. However, self-report adherence questionnaires are the most widely used indirect method due to their low cost and ease of implementation in both clinical and research settings (Lam & Fresco, 2015). Adherence is reported as a dichotomous variable (adherent/ non-adherent) and can be classified as low (poor) or high (good) (Nassar, Basheti, & Saini, 2022) (Anghel, 2019). This study assessed adherence rates with the use of two self-reported methods and their ability to predict viral suppression among participants in a clinical setting. The two adherence assessment methods employed were Morisky Medication Adherence Scale (MMAS-4) and visual analogue scale (VAS). Adherence level per adherence method were compared with level of viral load suppression.

Research Questions: What is the better tool for adherence measurements?

Research Hypothesis: Self-reported adherence by Morisky medication adherence Scale (MMAS-4) is statistically better than visual analogue scale (VAS) in measuring ART adherence.

Objective of the study: This study compared two commonly used self-report adherence measurement scales (Morisky medication adherence scale and the virtual analogue scale) in

predicting viral load suppression levels among children and young people in the South West Region of Cameroon.

Methodology

Study setting and population

This study was carried out in five high-volume HIV treatment Centres, one health facility each in Limbe, Tiko, Buea , Muyuka and Kumba health districts of the South West Region of Cameroon. The facilities were selected based on the enrolment of a high number of targeted children, adolescents, and young people. The study targeted children aged 0-9 years, adolescent aged 10-19 years and young people aged 20-24 years living with HIV and on antiretroviral treatment for at least six months. Participants or their caregivers were fully aware of their HIV status and had a valid viral load value at the time of data collection. Data of this study was collected for a period of six months from January to June 2023.

Study design and sampling

A facility-based cross-sectional and retrospective study was carried out. A retrospective component involved a record review in five health facilities that managed children and young people for HIV treatment. A probability proportionate to sample size was used to obtain the number of participants per site. A consecutive sampling was then used to select the participants in each of the selected health facilities. Based on a self-report adherence of 82% from a study carried out in the South West and North West Regions of Cameroon (Mbuwir Charlotte Bongfen, 2021), a total of 329 respondents were recruited from the five health facilities. The records of selected children, adolescents and young people were reviewed to obtain treatment regimens and viral load results.

Variable and Measurement

Demographic and treatment variables were collected using a structured questionnaire. Adherence in this study was defined as the client's ability to consistently swallow his or her medication, the right regimen and dose as prescribed and on time daily. Two adherence self-report tools were used. Non-adherence was normalized to minimize social desirability effects followed by an assessment of adherence to ART with the aid of Morisky medication adherence scale (MMAS-4) which consisted of four structured questions. Adherence was assessed through self-report by the client or by clients plus caregivers for younger children based on a 30-day recall period. Response to any of the questions was dichotomous (Yes/No) (Nassar, et al., 2022). A response of "No" in all the four questions rated client adherence as good, a "Yes" to one of the questions rated client adherence as moderate and a "Yes" to two or more of the questions signified poor adherence to ARV. For this scale, clients who have "No" responses to all four structured questions or "one "Yes" response to any of the questions were considered to be adherent to ART. While respondents who have two or more "Yes" responses to the four structured questions were considered to have poor or bad adherence to ART.

The second scale used in parallel to measure adherence on the same participant was the virtual analogue scale. This is another 30-day recall self-reported adherence assessment tool to measure client drug taking attitude. The scale is numbered 0-to-10 points with distinct marks on a straight line. A mark "X" on the zero mark on the line implied the child or adolescent did not swallow any drug, an 'X" mark on the number 5 on the line meant the client swallowed 50% of her medication for the past 30 days, a mark placed on the number 10 meant the client took all doses of her medication as prescribed which meant that the child/adolescent was 100% adherent to ART (Chkhartishvili N, 2014). Based on the score of the respondent on VAS, the respondent's adherence rate was categorized as optimal adherence ($\geq 90\%$), ART adherence moderate ($80 > 90$) and poor ART adherence ($< 80\%$). Based on these scales, participants who were categorised as having moderate or good ART adherence were considered adherent (Glass T, 2014) (Finitis DJ, 2016) (Giordano TP, 2004).

Participants' current viral load results valid within 6 months of sample collection and analysis were extracted from participants' medical records in the health facilities. A participant with viral load value of < 1000 copies per ml was considered virally suppressed and having good ART adherence.

Statistical Analysis

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Data was entered into Kobo collect, cleaned in Excel and analyzed in SPSS version 26. Adherence to antiretroviral therapy was measured using three scales namely visual analogue scale (score ranged from 0-10), adherence self-report (composed of 4 questions) and viral load (<1000copies/ml for suppressed and >1000copies/ml for unsuppressed).

A descriptive analysis was done. Frequency, mean, and ART adherence rates were determined among the participants per the three methods of adherence measurement.

Chi-square test was used to check the association between proportions. A multivariate logistic regression was used to check for factors associated to adherence. The Kendall's Wa concordance test was used to check the agreement between the three measures of adherence to ART. Also, the kappa statistics were used to check the agreement between viral load and the visual analogue scale and the MMAS-4 self-report scale. The percentage agreement was also determined manually between the three measures of adherence and between viral load and the other two measures of adherence. Statistically significant was set at $P \leq 0.05$.

Ethical considerations

Ethical approval for the study was obtained from the Institutional Review Board of the University of Bamenda. Administrative clearances were obtained from the Regional Delegation of Health, South West Region of Cameroon and the administrator or directors of the study health facilities. Written informed consent was obtained from adolescents and young adults older than 18 years. All the children and adolescents less than 18 years gave assent alongside informed consent from the parents or guardians.

Results and Discussion

4.1. Demographic characteristics of study participants

Of the 329 respondents who completed the questionnaires, 173 (52.9%) were females, 138 (41.9%) were within the age group 15-19 years, while 38 (11.6%) were below 10 years. The majority of the respondents were schooling with 209 (63.7%) in secondary and tertiary levels of education. Above average 204 (62.0%) were orphaned by at least one parent (Table 1).

Table 1: Socio-demographic characteristics of study participants

Variable	Categories	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Health facility	Buea- RH	51	15.5
	Kumba DH	80	24.3
	Limbe RH	65	19.8
	Mbingo Mutegene	88	26.7
	Muyuka DH	45	13.7
	Total	329	100
Sex	Female	173	52.9
	Male	154	47.1
	Total	327	100
Age group (years)	<10	38	11.6
	10_14	93	28.3
	15_19	138	41.9
	20_24	60	18.2
	Total	329	100
Educational level	None	11	3.4
	Primary	108	32.9
	Secondary	166	50.6
	Higher level	43	13.1
	Total	328	100
Occupation of the children/young people	Learning trade	45	13.7
	Employed	4	1.2
	Jobless	22	6.7
	Student/pupil	257	78.4
	Total	328	100
Orphan status	One parent is dead	124	37.7
	Both parents alive	125	38
	Both parents are dead	80	24.3
	Total	329	100

Alcohol consumption	No	282	86
	Yes	46	14
	Total	328	100
Quantity of Alcohol consumed	<3bottles a week	21	84
	3_6 bottles a week	4	16
	Total	25	100
Smoke Tobacco	No	325	98.8
	Yes	4	1.2
	Total	329	100

Clinical characteristics of study participants

For the mode of infection, 279 (84.8%) participants were infected through mother to child transmission and 155 (48.4%) started HIV treatment between 1-8 years. For the treatment regimen, 291 (88.4%) of respondents were on first line regimens and 38 (11.6%) were on second line regimens. Of the 318 participants who received treatment counselling, 197 (62.0%) received adherence counseling and psychosocial support at least three times in a year while 85 (26.7%) received adherence counseling and psychosocial supports in every clinic visit for the last one year.

About half, 159 (48.9%) of the participants have been on HIV treatment for at least 6 years with 211 (64.1%) of 329 respondents fully aware that they were living with HIV and 95 (28.9%) were sexually active (Table 2).

Table 2: Clinical Characteristics of Study Participants

Variable	Categories	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Mode of transmission	Other routes (blood transfusion, contaminated sharp)	17	5.2
	Horizontal (sexual route)	33	10
	Vertical (mother to child);	279	84.8
	Total	329	100
Initiation age (in years)	<1	48	15
	1_8	155	48.4
	9_16	89	27.8
	17_24	28	8.8
	Total	320	100
Duration on ARV treatment	>15	17	5.2
	1_5	75	23.1
	11_15	74	22.8

	6_10	159	48.9
	Total	325	100
ART Regimen	ABC/3TC/atvr	10	3
	Abc/3tc/dtg	52	15.8
	TDF/3TC/atvrr	18	5.5
	Tele	43	13.1
	TLD/atvr	8	2.4
	ABC/3TC/lpvr	2	0.6
	Azt/3tc/dtg	3	0.9
	Total	193	58.7
	Total	329	100
ART regimen line	First line	291	88.4
	Second line	38	11.6
	Total	329	100
Child know that she is living with HIV	No (partial disclosure)	118	35.9
	Yes (full disclosure)	211	64.1
	Total	329	100
age group of child fully disclosed	10_14	118	66.3
	15_19	41	23
	20_24	19	10.7
	Total	178	100
Child received therapeutic education/psychosocial support	None	36	11.3
	3 times	95	29.9
	6 times	102	32.1
	12 times	85	26.7
	Total	318	100
Child is sexually active	No	234	71.1
	Yes	95	28.9
	Total	329	100

Adherence to ARV of children, adolescents and young adults

Overall, 70.5 % of the participants responded “No” to four or three questions of the MMAS-4 structured questions and were classified as good adherence to ARV treatment.

For the self-report ARV adherence using virtual analogue scale, 69.0 % of the respondents reported having swallowed the medication on time at least 80-100 % of the time and were classified as having good adherence to ARV per the VAS and 31.0 % of respondents reported to have

swallowed their medication only at most 79 % during the 30 days evaluation period and were considered to have had poor adherence.

Based on the viral load count, 71.7 % of the respondents were virally suppressed (VL < 1000 copies/mL) while 29.3% of respondents were virally unsuppressed (VL ≥1000 copies/mL). Respondents who were virally suppressed were considered to have good adherent while respondents who have high viral load were considered to have poor adherence to ART (figure 1).

Figure 1: Adherence to ART among children, adolescents and young adults

Relationships between the three adherence measurements

The agreement level between the results obtained from the three measuring tools was examined both manually and by statistical tests. Manually, an estimated 74.8 % of the respondents’ results agreed between subjective adherence methods, 67.2 % of children and young peoples’ results agreed between self -reported Morisky medication adherence scale and viral load, while 72.9% of respondents’ results agreed between visual analogue scale and viral load suppression. Only 57.4 % of respondents ‘results agreed on all the three methods (Table 3).

Based on Kappa statistical test of concordance, there was poor agreement between the three adherence measurements tools (20-40%). The agreement between the two subjective methods was better (40.2%). Some level of agreement was also observed between visual analogue scale and viral load (35.2%) (Table 4).

Table 3: Agreement between the different adherence methods

Adherence	Agreement	n	% agreement
SR and VAS	Agree	246	74.8
	Disagree	83	25.2
	Total	329	100
SR and VL	Agree	221	67.2
	Disagree	108	32.8
	Total	329	100
VAS and VL	Agree	240	72.9
	Disagree	89	27.1
	Total	329	100
SR/VAS/VL	Agree	189	57.4
	Disagree	140	42.6
	Total	329	100

SR= self-report, VAS= visual analogue scale

Table 4: Level of agreement between the different methods of adherence obtained by Statistical test.

Adherence	Kappa	p-value	% agreement	Level of agreement
SR and VAS	0.402	<0.001	40.2%	Poor
SR and VL	0.201	<0.001	20.1%	Poor
VAS and VL	0.352	<0.001	35.2%	Poor

SR= self –report; VAS= visual Analogue Scale; VL =Viral Load

Association between the objective method (viral load) and the two subjective methods of adherence measures

There was a significant association between adherence self-report ($\chi=13.297$, $p<0.001$), adherence by visual analogue scale (VAS) ($\chi=40.928$, $p<0.001$) and adherence by viral load (Table 5).

Table 5: Association between viral load and the subjective methods of adherence

Variable	Categories	n	Viral Load		Unsuppressed	%	Chi-square	P-value
			Suppressed	%				
Adherence rate by self-report	Good	232	180	54.71	52	15.81	13.297	<0.001
	Poor	97	56	17.02	41	12.46		
	Total	329	236	71.73	93	28.27		
Adherence rate by VAS	Good	227	187	56.84	40	12.16	40.928	<0.001
	Poor	102	49	14.89	53	16.11		
	Total	329	236	71.73	93	28.27		

SR= self-report, VAS= visual analogue scale

Discussion:

The ART adherence among children and young people in this study was suboptimal with values ranging from 69.0 % to 71.7 % across the three assessment methods. This finding was consistent with that obtained in previous studies conducted by Lantche et al, 2021 and Mbuwir et al 2021 who identified suboptimal adherence levels of 66.3 % and 82.9 % respectively among adolescents in Cameroon.

Furthermore, the finding was also consistent with ART adherence levels of 73.3%, 66 %, 63.7% observed in children and adolescents in Ethiopia, south Africa and India respectively (Muktar Abadiga, 2019) (Achappa B, 2013) (Cluver, et al., 2021).

Globally, adherence levels found in this study were similar to 62.3 % adherence level obtained in a systematic review and meta-analysis conducted by Kim and his colleagues (Kim, Gerver, Fidler,

& Ward, 2014). Unlike findings of many studies in which adherence self-report is always higher due to social desirability, self-reported adherence in our study was lower (Buscher, n, Kallen, & Giordano, 2011) (Farmer, 1999) (Kim, Gerver, Fidler, & Ward, 2014) (Mbengue MAS, et al., 2019).

Children and adolescents faced bigger challenges adhering to medication and many factors account for this suboptimal adherence. Factors such as age, non-HIV disclosure, forgetfulness, peer pressure, pill burden and dependency on caregivers may account for this suboptimal adherence in study participants. Children and adolescents may possess limited knowledge and capacity to evaluate the impact of poor adherence on their health and destiny. Non-adherence in this study was normalized to the understanding of each participant before ART adherence assessment. This art potentially minimized the effects of recall bias, response bias and permitted the respondents to provide true report of medication-taking behavior without being judged.

Contrary, the adherence rates obtained in our study were not similar to the high (97%, 100 %) self-reported adherence observed among adolescents on ART in randomized control trial studies in Southern Uganda and South Africa conducted by Kizito et al and Orrell et al respectively (Kizito, Namuwonge, Brathwaite, Torsten B. Neilands, & Proscovia Nabunya, 2022) (Orrell.C, Cohen, & Leisegang, 2017). The wide difference observed in self-reported adherence could be due to the fact that our study was a cross-sectional study that happened under real-world conditions as opposed to the strictly controlled conditions in clinical trials resulting in proper follow-up and optimal ART adherence.

Based on Kappa statistical test of concordance, there was poor agreement (20-40%) between the three adherence measurement tools. The agreement between the two subjective methods was better (40.2%). Some level of agreement was also observed between visual analogue scale and viral load. This finding was not consistent with the high agreement levels of 66.0 % and 77.7% obtained in previous studies conducted in Cameroon by Mbuwir et al,2021 and Uganda by Kizito et al respectively (Mbuwir Charlotte Bongfen, 2021) (Kizito, Namuwonge, Brathwaite, Torsten B. Neilands, & Proscovia Nabunya, 2022). Mbuwir and her colleagues determined agreement between self-report and medication possession ratio among adolescents on ART in Cameroon while Kizito compared agreement between self-report adherence and Wisepill count among adolescents on ART in Uganda. This finding suggest that subjective measures (self-report MMAS-

4 and VAS) of adherence will not produce similar results when use in a similar population under similar conditions and context. Although there was poor concordance among the three tests, viral load had the highest mean rank while self-report had the least.

Respondents who had good ART adherence by VAS were approximately 40 times as likely to achieve viral suppression and respondents who had good ART adherence on MMAS-4 self-report were approximately 13 times as likely to achieve viral suppression. This finding confirms the fact that good adherence is the main determinant of viral suppression among children, adolescents and young people living with HIV on antiretroviral therapy. This result suggests as well that adolescents who were adherent per the virtual analogue scale have a higher probability of achieving viral suppression and treatment success as was reported in a previous study (Walsh JC, 2002). The visual analogue scale drew attention for children and adolescents in clinical setting and could have given a better opportunity to respondents to provide honest reports of medication-taking habit. A very high score of more than 90% per visual analogue scale was very feasible because the scale is easy, cheap and 100 % adherence per VAS can be a good proxy in predicting viral load suppression in clinical settings (Amico, et al., 2006).

In this study however, approximately 27.9 % of study participants who were adherent to ARV were not virally suppressed, implying that poor adherence might not be the only predictor of virologic failure in children and young people on HIV treatment. Other factors such as HIV drug resistance, limited medication potency and drug-drug interaction copies/mL may also account for Virologic failure (Lailulo, Kitenge, Jaffer, Aluko, & Nyasulu, 2020) (Nega, Taye, Million, & al., 2020).

Respondents who reported good ART adherence as low as 80% were virally suppressed in this study suggestive of high potency of pediatric ARV drug formulations currently in use in Cameroon compared to earlier pediatric ARV formulations that required the child to swallow at least 95% of the medication to achieve optimal adherence and viral suppression (Kim, Gerver, Fidler, & Ward, 2014).

Limitations

This study was a cross sectional and it was difficult to establish causality between adherence and viral suppression. An estimated 15.8% and 12.1% of respondents who were adherent by MMAS-4 self-report and VAS respectively did not achieve viral suppression and could not be attributed to undiagnosed treatment failure and ARV drug resistance. The study did not test the presence of ARV drugs in the blood or hair to determine the cause of unsuppressed viral load among respondents who reported optimal consumption (good adherence) of ARV drugs.

The findings of this study might have been influenced by some level of recall bias given the fact that two subjective measures were used. Respondents most often give positive responses to appear good (social desirability) before the clinician or the researcher thereby leading to overestimation of good adherence. This bias was mitigated by normalizing non-adherence to medication before ART adherence assessment.

Conclusions

Adherence to ART was low (69.0 -71.7 %) in children, adolescents and young people in both the subjective adherence measurements and the objective measurement (viral load count).

The subjective measurements (self-reported adherence) did not agree with the objective measurement (viral load suppression) indicating that subjective adherence assessment in clinical setting should be accompanied with viral load test in accordance with national algorithm to minimize delay identification and management of treatment failure and resistance.

A greater proportion of adolescents who were adherent by Visual analogue scale were virally suppressed indicating that in the absence of viral load testing facility in clinical settings, a highly adherent adolescent by visual analogue has higher chances of predicting viral suppression and good treatment outcomes.

Recommendation: There is need to develop strategies to improve ART adherence in children, adolescents and young adults in this setting. Further research with larger sample size should be conducted to determine effective methods of ART adherence assessment in HIV treatment centers of the South West Region.

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List of Abbreviations

ARV _ Antiretro viral

ART—Antiretro viral Therapy

ALHIV- Adolescents living with HIV.

HIV – Human immune virus

MMAS- Morisky Medication Adherence Scale

VAS – Visual Analogue Scale.

VS – Viral suppression